

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Some α -Hydroxy Acids by Acid Permanganate

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Kinetic studies have been done on the oxidation of some methyl and phenyl substituted glycollic acid derivatives like lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric, mandelic and benzoic acids by permanganate in acid medium. The influence of several factors such as acidity, salts and temperature on the reaction rate has been studied and the results all indicate that intermediate manganese ions such as Mn(III) are the active oxidising species. A tentative mechanism for the reactions has been suggested.

The vigour of the reactions under identical condition are in the order : α -hydroxy isobutyric acid < glycollic acid < lactic acid < mandelic acid < benzoic acid.

THE oxidation reactions of several α -hydroxy acids by different ions of transition metals have been investigated in details by different workers and these have been reviewed by Waters *et al.*¹. Recently chromic acid oxidation of several α -hydroxy acids have been reported²⁻⁴. However, the details of the oxidation of the same substrates by permanganate are not known in the literature although some preliminary studies of the oxidation of few α -hydroxy acids have been reported earlier⁵⁻⁷. Most of the investigations have been carried out at very low acid concentrations. It is unlikely, however, that manganese (III) which is stable $\geq 1.0M$ acid would remain stable at around pH 4 at which reactions were carried out by earlier workers⁵⁻⁷. The present paper concerns with the oxidation of some methyl and phenyl substituted derivatives of glycollic acid in high mineral acid concentrations in an attempt to have some information about the mechanism of the oxidation reactions. The reaction of benzoic acid with permanganate is too fast to be studied in details under the conditions at which other hydroxy compounds have been studied and some preliminary reports have been furnished for benzoic acid oxidation.

Experimental

Reagents : Redistilled water from dilute alkaline permanganate was used. Potassium permanganate was of G.R. (E.Merck) grade α -hydroxy acids and all other reagents were of B.D.H. grades.

Potassium permanganate solution was standardised by oxalate method and α -hydroxy acids by the acid-alkali titrations using phenolphthalein as indicator.

Kinetic measurements

The course of the reaction was followed spectrophotometrically with a Carl Zeiss VSU2 model spectrophotometer from the measurement of the optical densities of the reaction mixture at 530 nm. Quartz cell of path length 5 cm. for benzoic acid and 1 cm for other hydroxy acids were used. The substrates had no absorption at 530 nm.

Results and Discussion

Products of reaction : The products of the reactions in excess substrate concentrations (the experimental condition used in kinetic experiments) were acetaldehyde, acetone, benzaldehyde and benzophenone for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric, mandelic and benzoic acids respectively. These products had been identified by preparation of their 2 : 4 DNP derivatives.

Influence of reactant concentration : The initial reaction of permanganate with lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acids are all of first order with respect to both the reactants. These orders at the beginning have been determined by measuring the reaction rate (from the slope of the tangent to the reaction time curve) at different initial concentrations of permanganate and substrate. The plots of initial rate, $\left[\frac{-d(\text{O.D.})}{dt} \right]_i$ against initial optical density, $(\text{O.D.})_i$ for experiments with different oxidant concentrations and fixed substrate concentrations give straight lines (Figure 2) passing through the origin, showing the order with respect to permanganate to be one at the start. The ratios initial rate/[Sub.] at different concentrations of substrate but with fixed concentration of oxidant are recorded in Table 1.

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These values have been computed to be $(6.41 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-1}$, $(4.35 \pm 0.1) \times 10^{-1}$ and (13.1 ± 0.2) lit. mole⁻¹ min⁻¹, for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acids respectively, which are fairly constant to exhibit that order with respect to substrate is one

The sigmoid reaction-time curves (Fig. 1) indicate that with the progress of the reaction the initial second order kinetics is followed by a more complex kinetics. The order of the reaction with respect to substrate and permanganate have also been determined near the region where the reaction rate is

Fig. 1. Effect of manganous ion on the reaction :

- (a) $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 3.77 \times 10^{-4}M$, $[\text{Lactic acid}] = 3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 29.5°.
- (b) $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 4.60 \times 10^{-4}M$, $[\alpha\text{-hydroxy isobutyric acid}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 28°.
- (c) $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 3.63 \times 10^{-4}M$, $[\text{Mandelic acid}] = 8.33 \times 10^{-4}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 28.5°.

a, *b* and *c* (hollow figures) represent the reaction-time curves for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acid respectively while *a'*, *b'* and *c'* (corresponding solid figures) represent the same in presence of $9.2 \times 10^{-5}M$, $7.1 \times 10^{-5}M$ and $7.86 \times 10^{-5}M$ MnSO_4 respectively.

Fig. 2. Effect of oxidant on the initial reaction rate :

- (a) $[\text{Lactic acid}] = 6.67 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 30.5°.
- (b) $[\alpha\text{-hydroxy isobutyric acid}] = 3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 28°.
- (c) $[\text{Mandelic acid}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 29°.

a, *b* and *c* represent the plots of initial rate vs. initial O.D. for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acid respectively.

maximum and are found to be 0.81, 1.2 and 0.48 with respect to permanganate and 0.075, 0.98 and 0.59 with respect to substrate for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acids respectively. The plots of $1/\text{rate}$ vs. $1/[\text{sub.}]$ (Fig. 5) near the same region give straight lines having intercepts in case of

TABLE I—EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE ON THE INITIAL RATES

(a)	$[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 3.77 \times 10^{-4}M$	$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$	Temp. = 30.5°				
(b)	$[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 5.12 \times 10^{-4}M$	$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$	Temp. = 28°				
(c)	$[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 3.24 \times 10^{-4}M$	$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$	Temp. = 29°				
<i>a</i>	$[\text{Lactic acid}] \times 10^3M$	3.33	4.00	5.00	6.67	7.50	10.00
	Initial rate $\times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)	2.07	2.58	3.31	4.30	4.70	6.45
	$\frac{\text{Initial rate}}{[\text{Lactic acid}]} \times 10^1$ (lit. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	6.22	6.45	6.62	6.45	6.27	6.45
<i>b</i>	$[\alpha\text{-hydroxy isobutyric acid}] \times 10^3M$		2.00	2.50	3.33	4.00	5.00
	Initial rate $\times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)		0.86	1.09	1.47	1.74	2.16
	$\frac{\text{Initial rate}}{[\alpha\text{-hydroxy isobutyric acid}]} \times 10^1$ (lit. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)		4.30	4.36	4.41	4.35	4.32
<i>c</i>	$[\text{Mandelic acid}] \times 10^3M$		0.833	0.909	1.00	1.11	1.25
	Initial rate $\times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)		1.09	1.19	1.30	1.48	1.61
	$\frac{\text{Initial rate}}{[\text{Mandelic acid}]} \times 10^1$ (lit. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)		131	131	130	133	129

Here and everywhere the rates are measured in terms of O.D. I.O. O.D. for 1 cm path length = $4.38 \times 10^{-4}M$ KMnO_4 .

lactic and mandelic acid while in case of isobutyric acid it passes through the origin. The intercept gives us a hint that the reaction proceeds through the formations of complex with the intermediate ions derived from permanganate ion in the cases of lactic and mandelic acid.

The order with respect to both substrate and oxidant at any intermediate stage of the reaction are determined from the consideration at the rate of the reaction at any intermediate stage is represented by :

$$\text{Rate} = k[\text{MnO}_4^-][\text{Sub}]^q[\text{Mn}^{+2}]^r$$

If experiments are carried out with different initial concentrations of permanganate but at fixed concentration of substrate and the rates are measured after a fixed change x of O.D. ($x = 0.4$ in our experiment) the plot of $\log(\text{rate})$ vs. $\log[(\text{O.D.})_i - x]$ will be a straight line (Fig. 3) with slope equal to p , which

Fig. 3. Effect of oxidant on the rate at intermediate stage : Compositions of the reaction mixtures are same as in figure 2. Here a , b and c represent the plots of reaction rate (after 0.4 change in O.D.) vs. $\log[(\text{O.D.})_i - 0.4]$, for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acid respectively.

is the order with respect to permanganate. For here $[\text{Mn}^{+2}]$ which results from the reduction of permanganate ion remains fixed after fixed change of O.D. and $[\text{substrate}]$ of course fixed. Similarly, by studying the reaction at different initial concentrations of substrate but with same initial concentration of permanganate q can be determined from the plot of $\log(\text{rate})$ vs. $\log[\text{Sub}]$ (Fig. 4) under the same condition i.e., after fixed change in O.D.

Effect of acidity : The reactions are studied in different concentrations of sulfuric acid. It is interesting to note that in the cases of α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acids the initial rate first decreases,

reaches a minimum and then increases with increase in acidity. While with lactic acid no such minimum is observed; the rate increases all along with increase in concentration of sulfuric acid (Fig. 6).

Fig. 4. Effect of substrate on the rate at intermediate stage : a , b and c represent the plots of $\log(\text{rate})$ vs. $\log[\text{Sub}]$ after 59%, 49% and 53% consumption of permanganate (the regions where the rates are maximum) for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acid respectively. The compositions of the reaction mixtures are given in the Table 1.

Influence of different salts : The effects of different salts like manganous sulfate, sodium fluoride and sodium sulfate on the reaction rates have been studied. The reactions are accelerated by manganous sulfate (Fig. 1) (excepting the case of benzilic acid where retardation is observed) and retarded by sodium fluoride (Table 2). Sodium sulfate has also a feeble retarding effect on the overall reaction (Table 3). We can account for all these effects of different salts and the sigmoid nature of the reaction-time curves if we assume that intermediate manganese ions such as Mn(III) which form stable complex with fluoride ions and feeble complex with sulfate ions are the principal species responsible for the oxidation.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SODIUM FLUORIDE ON THE REACTION RATE

(a)	$[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$, $[\text{Lactic}] = 6.67 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 20.5°.
(b)	$[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4}M$, $[\alpha\text{-hydroxy isobutyric}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 20.5°.—
(c)	$[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 4.45 \times 10^{-4}M$, $[\text{Mandelic}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 20.5°.
(d)	$[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 8.7 \times 10^{-5}M$, $[\text{Benzilic}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$, Temp. = 20.5°.
	$[\text{NaF}] \times 10^2M$ 0.0 1.0 2.0 4.0 10.0
(a)	56.1 21.9 16.1 10.8
(b)	41.4 6.3 2.4 1.5
(c)	22.2 14.5 12.3 10.1
(d)	51.0 29.5 19.9 13.9 9.2

a , b , c and d denote percentage of reaction after 45, 44, 15 and 1.75 min. respectively.

Fig. 5. Plot of $1/\text{rate}$ vs. $1/[\text{Sub}]$ at intermediate stage: Compositions of the reaction mixtures are same as in Table 1. Here rate and $[\text{Sub}]$ are the same as in Figure-4. a , b and c represent the plots for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acid respectively.

These intermediate manganese ions are supposed to be generated from the reaction between Mn^{+2} and MnO_4^- ions. Had MnO_4^- ions been the main reacting species a reduction in rate would have been observed in presence of added Mn^{+2} ions which reduce the concentration of MnO_4^- ions.

Kinetic studies have also been done on the oxidation of methyl and phenyl substituted glycollic acids by Mn(III) (prepared⁸ by the reaction between MnSO_4 and KMnO_4) and it has been found that under identical condition the time required for 90% consumption of oxidant is less in case of oxidation with Mn(III) than that in case of permanganate. That Mn(III) ions are the active oxidising species is corroborated from this observation. The term 'identical' implies same acidity, same concentration of substrate and equivalent concentration of oxidants. The initial concentration of Mn^{+2} ion in the reaction mixture is so maintained that the total concentration of Mn^{+2} ion after the completion of the reaction is the same in each case of oxidation.

Influence of temperature on the rate: The second order rate constants (k_2) at the beginning of the reaction at different temperatures are calculated from the rate expression. The energies of activation for the slow steps were calculated from the plots of $\log k_2$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 7) in case of lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acids and these together with other activation parameters are given in the Table 4. In case of benzoic acid (since it is too fast at ordinary temperature to get a reaction-time curve) the time (t) taken for 90% consumption of permanganate have been recorded at different temperatures and from the plot of $-\log t$ against $1/T$ (which has the same slope as the plot of $\log k$ against $1/T$), the energy of activation has been calculated to be 18.0 ± 1.4 kcal in this case.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SODIUM SULFATE

- (a) $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 5.25 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[\text{Lactic}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0 M$, Temp. = 30° .
- (b) $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 5.25 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[\alpha\text{-hydroxy isobutyric}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0 M$, Temp. = 28.5° .
- (c) $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 4.34 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[\text{Mandelic}] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0 M$, Temp. = 27.5° .

$[\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4] M \leftarrow \text{Rate} \times 10^2 (\text{min}^{-1}) \rightarrow$

	a	b	c
0.0	13.3	7.66	7.77
0.1	12.9	7.50	7.68
0.2	12.6	7.44	7.73
0.3	—	7.33	7.37
0.5	11.1	7.03	6.67

a , b and c denote the rates of reactions after 58%, 50% and 50% of reaction respectively.

Rate Expression and Mechanism

The effect of substrate and permanganate on the oxidation of lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acid at the beginning may be accommodated by the following rate expression:

$$\text{Rate} = k_2[\text{Sub}][\text{MnO}_4^-]$$

This is consistent with the following mechanism similar to that in case of glycollic acid⁹:

R = H, R' = CH₃ for lactic acid.
 R = R' = CH₃ for α -hydroxy isobutyric acid
 R = H, R' = C₆H₅ for mandelic acid.

Fig. 6. Effect of acidity on the reaction rate :

- (a) [Lactic acid] = $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ = $3.77 \times 10^{-4} M$, Temp. = 30.5° .
 (b) [α -hydroxy isobutyric acid] = $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ = $4.99 \times 10^{-4} M$, Temp. = 30° .
 (c) [Mandelic acid] = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ = $4.38 \times 10^{-4} M$, Temp. = 28° .

a, b and c represent the plots of initial rate vs. $\log [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acid respectively.

The effect of acidity though complex enough to be treated quantitatively may at least, be qualitatively explained in the light of the above mechanism. With increase in acidity of the medium the step (1) is facilitated while step (2) (which involves the liberation of a proton) is expected to be retarded with this increase in acidity. Due to this opposing effect of acidity on (1) and (2) the plot of reaction rate vs. $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ is expected to exhibit minimum as are found in the cases of α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acids. Again the change of acidity affects

Fig. 7. Effect of temperature on the reaction :

- (a) [Lactic acid] = $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ = $3.75 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = $3.0 M$.
 (b) [α -hydroxy isobutyric acid] = $6.8 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ = $5.05 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = $3.0 M$.
 (c) [Mandelic acid] = $6.2 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ = $2.45 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = $3.0 M$.
 (d) [Benzilic acid] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ = $1.01 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ = $1.5 M$.

a, b and c represent the plots of $\log k_2$ vs. $1/T$ for lactic, α -hydroxy isobutyric and mandelic acid respectively, while *d* represents the plot of $3 \log t$ vs. $1/T$ in case of benzilic acid. Here '*t*' is expressed in terms of second.

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Substrate	k_2 (lit. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹) at 303°K	pZ (lit. mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	E (kcal)	ΔS^\ddagger (e.u.)	ΔG^\ddagger (kcal) at 303°K
Lactic acid	2.95 ± 0.1	$(5.37 \pm 35.0) \times 10^{11}$	15.6 ± 1.2	-15.2 ± 4.0	19.6 ± 0.02
α -hydroxy isobutyric acid	0.488 ± 0.02	$(1.34 \pm 10.8) \times 10^{15}$	21.4 ± 1.3	$+0.66 \pm 4.3$	20.6 ± 0.03
Mandelic acid	64.0 ± 2.5	$(8.63 \pm 69.4) \times 10^{14}$	18.2 ± 1.3	-0.33 ± 4.3	17.7 ± 0.02
Benzilic acid	—	—	18.0 ± 1.4	—	—

step (2) more than (1) at lower acidity and as such the minimum if it is observed at all should be observed at lower acid region. The position of minimum in case of lactic acid is perhaps shifted to such lower acidity where it is not possible to carry out the reaction homogeneously due to precipitation of MnO_2 and therefore it is not observed.

The step (2) of the above mechanism will be retarded if R or R' be methyl while it will be accelerated if R or R' be phenyl in comparison to the parent glycollic acid (from the pK values of the acids). Our experimental fact is that due to the introduction of one methyl or phenyl group into glycollic acid the reaction rate is increased. The rate is further increased if two phenyl groups are introduced ($R = R' = C_6H_5$) while if both R and R' be methyl the rate is decreased even below that in case of parent glycollic acid. This is only possible if the formation and decomposition of the manganate ester is affected in the same direction by phenyl substitution and in the opposite direction by methyl substitution. That is, the formation of the manganate ester will take place in such a manner that it will be favoured in case of both methyl and phenyl substitution. This is possible only if it is formed by S_N^1 mechanism and not by S_N^2 mechanism. For in the latter case the formation of the ester would be favoured in case of phenyl while it will be opposed in case of methyl substitution and in that case introduction of both one and two methyl groups would have decreased the reaction rate.

The above mechanism explains the order of reactivity of glycollic acid and its substituted derivatives. However, in case of hydroxy acids $RCH(OH)CO_2H$ ($R = H, CH_3, C_6H_5$) the possibility of another mechanism similar to that found in case of oxidation of alcohol^{10, 11} by acid permanganate, which involves the rupture of a $\alpha-C-H$ bond in the rate determining step, cannot be ruled out.

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